

THE GLOBAL FAME OF ALISHER NAVOIY'S WORK AND THEIR TRANSLATION INTO MULTIPLE LANGUAGES

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Abstract: *This article is about fame of Alisher Navoiy and his contribution to the world literature. It explores that Alisher Navoiy has a lot to do with the existence of Turkic language not to mention his poetry that inspired many foreign scholars. In addition, this article underlines some translating methods as well as some challenges which can call into being while translating process. Ultimately, the article emphasizes the importance of preserving and promoting Navoiy's legacy as a bridge between Eastern and western literary traditions.*

Key words: *Alisher Navoiy, poetry translation, universal themes, sufi philosophy, translation challenges.*

Introduction: Alisher Navoiy is one of the most famous writers in history. He is known as the brightest star of Uzbek literature and the founder of Turkic classical literature. He lived in the 15th century and wrote many poems and books. Navoiy showed that the Chagatai language (an early form of Uzbek) could be as beautiful and strong as Persian, the popular language at that time. His best work, the “ Khamsa “ (Quintet), includes five poems about love, justice, and humanity. Today, his works are read and loved not only in Uzbekistan but all around the world.

In his time, Alisher Navoiy elevated the Chagatai language in the peak of literature. This language was used as a literary and scientific medium across Central Asia, Turkey and even parts of India. His “ Khamsa “, written in Turkic, was the first masterpiece in this language and gained great popularity in the Eastern world. These works were soon admired in Persian and Arabic as well.

Alisher Navoiy's contribution to world literature. Alisher Navoiy's works are still important today. His ideas about human life, love, justice and knowledge continue to be relevant to place around the world. According to Canadian literary expert R. N. Frye [1], Navoiy, not only in

his own language but throughout the East, brought poetry to a new level. His poems combine literary experience with philosophical depth, showing great artistic value. Frye recognized Navoiy's works as classical works of Eastern poetry and emphasized that they are part of global cultural heritage. His works have been translated into different languages like Russian, English, French and German. This has allowed readers in many countries to enjoy his writings, not only in Central Asia but also in Europe, North America and other places. Navoiy's writings continue to inspire writers and thinkers today. His style and ideas have shaped both Turkic and Persian literature. One of the leaders of Uzbek Jadid movement, Fitrat, highly valued Alisher Navoiy's legacy and writes: "Navoiy, through his poetry, demonstrated the potential of the Turkic language and introduced it to the world as a great literary tool" [2]. Navoiy's works are not only important for literature but also for philosophy and even politics. His thoughts on justice and fairness are still used by people today to discuss social issues. His works are often mentioned in films, music and other art forms, showing that his ideas are still alive in modern culture. For example, the 1947 Soviet film Alisher Navoiy directed by Kamil Yarmatov depicts the life and contributions of Navoiy. The film highlights his commitment to literature, justice and cultural development, portraying him as a national hero of Uzbekistan. As well as the Uzbek composer Mutal Burhonov created symphonies and operas based on Navoiy's poetry and legacy, showcasing his enduring influence on Uzbek music.

Navoiy's were not just confined to the Turkish – speaking world; they made their way into Western literary circles through translations and scholarly studies. His ideas on justice, love and human nature align with many Western philosophical and literary traditions. His poetry influenced notable European intellectuals, especially during the 19th and 20th centuries when there was a renewed interest in Eastern literature. Many of Navoiy's themes transcend cultural boundaries, resonating with Western audiences as much as they do with Eastern ones. For example:

Love and sacrifice: In his famous Layli and Majnun, Navoiy explores the theme of external love, a topic that is central to Western literature as well. Romeo and Juliet by Shakespeare can be a bright example [3]. His portrayal of love as both a transcendent and human experience parallels Western romantic traditions.

Justice and moral philosophy: Navoiy's emphasis on justice and fair leadership, especially in works like Nasihatnama, aligns with Western

moral philosophy, particularly that of thinkers like Plato and Aristotle, who also focused on the role of virtue in Governance. Plato discusses justice extensively in his famous work *The Republic*. In this book Plato argues that justice means everyone performing their assigned role in society without interfering with other's roles. According to him, philosophers are the best rulers because they possess wisdom and a deep understanding of justice. He uses "The allegory of the cave" metaphor to show how philosophers, as seekers of truth, can guide society toward justice and enlightenment [4]. Aristotle discusses justice in *Nicomachean Ethics*. He considered justice the most important virtue, as it ensures fairness and equality in society. In his book, he wrote about two types of justice: Distributive justice: Fair distribution of resources based on merit.

Rectificatory justice: Correcting wrongs through fairness in transactions or punishments. By this, Aristotle emphasized balance and avoiding extremes, which ties into a leader's responsibility to act moderately and fairly [5]. Both Plato and Aristotle focused on the moral qualities of leaders and their role in creating a just society. Similarly, Alisher Navoiy in *Nasihatnama* highlights justice as the foundation of effective governance, aligning with these classical ideas.

Humanism and individualism: In his poetry, Navoiy consistently emphasizes human dignity and the individual's place in the world, concepts that were central to Renaissance and Western humanism. His works stress the importance of self-reflection, personal growth and understanding one's moral duties, which resonates with the ideas of Renaissance thinkers like Erasmus and even existentialists like Sartre. Erasmus believed that individuals should seek wisdom and live virtuous lives, stressing the value of introspection and the cultivation of personal morality. Erasmus' ideas mirror Navoiy's in their focus on personal growth, responsibility and self-reflection [6]. Navoiy's stress on self-awareness and moral duties parallels Erasmus' views. For instance, Navoiy's poetry often urges individuals to reflect on their actions. Sartre's philosophy emphasizes personal responsibility and the individual's freedom to make choices, with a focus on self-reflection. His ideas center on the individual's ability to shape their own identity and destiny, aligning with Navoiy's emphasis on moral reflection and the importance of one's actions in shaping society [7]. Navoiy's call for personal growth and understanding one's duties mirrors Sartre's existentialist idea that the individual must take responsibility for their actions and shape their moral framework. Just like Sartre, Navoiy

stress individual moral development as a means of to contribute positively to society. As for Uzbek scholars opinion, Oybek highlighted Navoiy`s role in his time and culture. He stated: “The ideas of humanism in Navoiy`s works, his promotion of human rights and justice, make his poetry timeless”. Oybek saw love and justice in Navoiy`s poetry as universal values that apply to all humanity [8]. Also the well –known educator Abdulla Avloniy emphasized the importance of teaching Navoiy`s works to young people. According to him, great poets like Navoiy lead us toward true humanity and national pride through their works. Reading his poetry is, above all, understanding ourselves [9]

Translation history. Alisher Navoiy`s works were first translated into Persian, Arabic and Turkish during his lifetime and shortly after. These translations helped spread his ideas across the Islamic world. Scholar and poets in these regions studied his works, making him a well –known figure in literature and philosophy. As given an example, 16th century Turkish poet Fuzuli studied Navoiy`s works in Turkish and Persian. Inspired by Navoiy`s themes of love, sipirituality and moral philosophy, he adopted similar styles in his poetry. His famous work Leyla and Majnun reflects the depth of emotion and philosophical thought often seen in Navoiy`s writings. What`s more, Russian scholars like Wilhelm Barthold and V.V.Bartold translated and analyzed Navoiy`s works, bringing his philosophy and literary genius to the attention of European readers. Their studies helped establish Navoiy`s role as a bridge between Eastern and Western literary traditions [10].

In the 20th century, translations of his works expanded to other languages like English, French and German. These translations allowed Navoiy`s messages of justice, love and humanity to reach a global audiences. One notable example is Jean –Baptiste Nicolas, French scholar, who translated Navoiy`s ghazals, emphasized the universal themes of love, justice and human dignity present in Navoiy`s poetry, making it accessible to French audiences and inspiring Romantic poets in Europe [11]. German Orientalists, such as Friedrich Ruckert, studied Navoiy`s poetry as part of their exploration of sufi literature. Ruckert`s translations highlighted Navoiy`s deep philosophical reflections and his contribution to Eastern mysticism. His work inspired German readers to delve into sufi concepts of divine love and unity, bridging Eastern and Western philosophical traditions [12].

Translations played an important role in introducing Navoiy`s works to different cultures. They showed that his ideas were not limited to one

region or language – they had a global appeal. His works become a bridge between the East and West, connecting different traditions and philosophies. Challenges in translating Alisher Navoiy's works. Translating Alisher Navoiy's works is a difficult process because his poetry is full of deep meanings, beautiful language and musical flow. Translators face several challenges when working with his texts: Navoiy's poetry often has multiple layers of meaning. His words carry symbolic messages and spiritual ideas. Translators must work hard to show this depth in another language because each language has its unique way of expressing ideas. What's more, the rhythm and musicality of the original poetry may not be suitable in the new language. As given an example, Navoiy often uses the images of "rose and nightingales", which symbolize not only love but also the connection between humans and divine. Sometimes it can be challenging to explain these meanings in a translation. That's why translators often use specific methods to make the translations clear and meaningful. These methods are divided into two groups:

1. Adaptation: This means changing the original text slightly to make it more clear and understandable for readers in a new language or culture. Alisher Navoiy's "Farhod and Shirin" can be an example for this method. In some translations, cultural parts like "dastarkhan" are replaced with words like "banquet" or "feast" to make it familiar to readers in English or French.

2. Explanatory translation: In this method, translators keep the original text but add explanations to clarify cultural or symbolic meanings. For example, Edward . G. Browne, who translated Navoiy's sufi poetry into English, included explanations about sufi terms like "tariqat" (spiritual path) or "ma`rifat" (divine knowledge) to help readers understand the spiritual context [13].

Methodology: The name of method is "Be a translator of Navoiy". In this method, we will take a ruboiy (four-line poem) in Uzbek and this poem has to be translated into English. For example:

Suvdek ochiq qalbingdan oshyon topsam,
Jahon to`la nurlar sochilgan manzara topsam,
Shunday qalb sohibi borman, demak, sharaf,
Sadoqat yo`lida sizdek yo`ldosh topsam.

Here is the translations of some words and phrases:

Oshyon - shelter

Ochiq qalb - open-hearted

Nurlar sochilgan - light scattered

Sharaf - noble

Sadoqat yo`li - loyalty`s path

Yo`ldosh - companion

Translated ruboiy in English:

If I find shelter in you open-hearted soul,
A world of light scattered, a glorious goal.
To have a heart so noble, what an honor it is
In loyalty`s path, a companion like you to console.

In translating this ruboiy, the primary focus was to retain the emotional depth and imagery of the original. Maintaining the rhyme scheme was challenging but essential to preserve the poetic essence. Metaphors like “suvdek ochiq qalb” (an open-hearted soul like water) were translated directly to reflect their universality.

This ruboiy reflects Navoiy`s emphasis on loyalty, love and human connection – universal themes that align with the article`s exploration of his global influence. By translating the ruboiy, the article demonstrates how Navoiy`s work transcends linguistic barriers while retaining its profound philosophical message.

Conclusion: Alisher Navoiy`s works are not only a part of Uzbek literature but also a treasure for the whole world. His poetry and ideas about justice, human dignity, and personal growth have inspired people for ages. Through translations into many languages, his works have crossed borders, connecting Eastern and Western cultures.

However, translating Navoiy`s poetry is not easy. Translators must work hard to keep the meaning, beauty and emotions alive in other languages. Despite these challenges, their efforts have made Navoiy`s messages of love, unity and wisdom accessible to all.

Studying Alisher Navoiy reminds us that literature is a bridge between cultures and that his timeless ideas are as meaningful today as they were in his time. By continuing to explore and share his works, we can ensure that his legacy will inspire future generations around the world.

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